

Climate-friendly and resilient fisheries
through innovation and co-learning

infinifish.eu

Data management plan

Infinifish deliverable D1.1, version 1 (2025-08-29)

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1	2025-08-29	First version submitted to the European Commission.

About Infinifish

The project *Climate-friendly and resilient fisheries through innovation and co-learning*, short name *Infinifish*, is an innovation action funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe research programme under Grant Agreement number 101181077. Its objective is to create innovations to monitor and mitigate the impacts of fishing on the climate and enable fishers to adapt to the consequences of climate change. To learn more about the project, its participants, and its results, please visit the Infinifish web site at <https://infinifish.eu> and the CORDIS project fact sheet and results database at <https://doi.org/10.3030/101181077>.

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1 Introduction

This is the data management plan (DMP) for the *Infinifish* project. Its purpose is to help ensure that data generated or reused in the project are handled in accordance with applicable rules and regulations, the Grant Agreement,¹ and with core principles of Open Science such as *open data*, *open access publication*, and *open source software*.

The DMP provides an overview of the data the project is expected to generate or reuse, a description of the infrastructure and procedures the project will employ to ensure that the data is safeguarded and preserved, and guidelines to assist the project partners and their personnel in good, ethical data handling.

This is a living document that will be updated regularly as the project progresses. Three versions of the DMP will be submitted as formal deliverables: D1.1 at the start of the project, D1.2 about halfway through the project period, and D1.3 when the project ends.

The document is structured as follows:

- Section 2 defines key roles and terms associated with data handling.
- Section 3 provides an overview of the data that will be generated or reused in the project and the purposes for doing so.
- Section 4 describes how data will be stored and shared during the project period, and the conditions under which data will be archived.
- Section 5 describes how data will be disseminated openly through public repositories in accordance with the FAIR principles.
- Section 6 discusses ethical aspects in general, and handling of personal information in particular.
- Section 7 describes the allocation of resources needed for data handling and storage.

Project participants involved in data collection, processing, or use should pay particular attention to sections 4–6. These sections outline the partners' responsibilities for data handling and compliance with the Grant Agreement, the GDPR, and open science principles.

¹ The Grant Agreement is the contract between the project partners and the funding body, the European Research Executive Agency.

2 Definitions

2.1 Roles and responsibilities

SINTEF Ocean is the *coordinator* of Infinifish and has the overall responsibility for data management. Currently, the role of Coordinator² is inhabited by [Lars T. Kyllingstad](#), who is also the Data Manager.

The *partners* include the coordinator and other beneficiaries of the Grant Agreement. All partners are responsible for contributing to good data management in accordance with this DMP.

The *granting authority* is the European Research Executive Agency (REA), under powers delegated by the European Commission.

The Communication and Dissemination Manager is responsible for monitoring and coordinating the project's dissemination efforts to make sure that the results get propagated through the right channels at the right time. This role is currently held by [Hanne Hjelle Hatlebrekke](#), SINTEF Ocean.

The project's Innovation and Exploitation Manager has a responsibility for helping the partners to identify business opportunities arising from the project results and determine whether some data need to be protected for such opportunities to be exploited. Currently, the Innovation and Exploitation Manager is [Mira Elina Willert Søråsen](#), SINTEF Ocean.

2.2 Terminology and scope

2.2.1 Data

For the purposes of this DMP, *data* includes all digital information and materials generated or used during the project. This includes (but is not limited to)

- raw measurements, logs, and instrument outputs
- processed datasets and derived products
- outputs of simulations
- recordings and transcripts of interviews and workshops
- software source code and scripts
- protocol specifications and methodologies

² Capital C intended to distinguish the person from the organisation.

- configuration files and computational workflows
- photos, videos, audio, and other media
- papers, reports, and other documents

2.2.2 Classification

For the purposes of this DMP, we define three information classification levels:

- *Public* data can be shared publicly.
- *Internal* data can be shared freely within the consortium and with the granting authority.
- *Restricted* data may only be shared with specific companies or persons.

“Sensitive” will be used to mean “internal or restricted” when the distinction is not relevant. This use overlaps with the information classification level of the same name described in Article 13 of the Grant Agreement.

The Grant Agreement also describes a level called “classified” which refers to information that is classified under [Commission Decision 2015/444](#) of 13 March 2015 on the security rules for protecting EU classified information. As we do not expect the generation of any such data within the project, no dedicated infrastructure has been established for its management, and a corresponding classification level is not provided.

2.2.3 Data set

We will use the term “data set” to refer to a collection of data that is generated, collected, or used for a particular purpose. For example, a data set could be the data that are collected during a trial, the data that are associated with a certain technology, or the data that are used in a particular task.

2.2.4 Size

It is difficult to say upfront how much data will be generated by research activities, yet it is useful to have *some* estimate to plan for appropriate storage and sharing facilities. Here, we will use the following semi-quantitative size categories, based on order-of-magnitude estimation and practical considerations:

- *Small*: up to tens of megabytes; shareable via email
- *Medium*: hundreds of megabytes; shareable via regular file sharing services
- *Large*: gigabytes or more; needs special data sharing services

3 Data overview

In this section, we provide an overview of the data that is expected to be generated or reused in the project, the purposes for doing so, and the extent to which the data will be made public.

More detailed information about each data set will be registered in a common database available to all project partners. This includes information about the format, size, and classification of the data sets, their provenance and ownership, how they will be used, how they will be stored and shared during and after the project period, and how partners may access them.

3.1 Purpose of data generation and use

Data will be generated and used in Infinifish only insofar as doing so will help to achieve the project objectives. These objectives are:

1. Adapt and validate innovative fishing gear technologies to reduce fuel intensity and seabed impact in demersal trawl fisheries.
2. Develop and validate decision support systems (DSS) to reduce fuel intensity and increase fuel efficiency in a wide variety of fisheries.
3. Develop and validate fish processing technologies and products that increase the efficiency of resource utilisation.
4. Investigate the impacts of climate change on ecosystems and fisheries, incorporating the effects of innovative technologies.
5. Improve the uptake of new technologies in European fisheries through co-learning.

The immediate outcomes of the project include the development of

- 11 *technological innovations* to reduce the climate impact of fishing and increase the fishing sector's resiliency against climate change
- 3 *ecosystem simulation platforms* for assessing adaptation strategies, fishing mortality levels, and management actions, providing updateable outcomes informing stakeholders and supporting decision making
- a *policy action plan* to facilitate adaptations and the adoption of new technologies within the fishing industry

Collectively, these are called the *key exploitable results*, or KERs, of Infinifish.

The following are the 11 technological innovations that will be developed/adapted and validated within the project:

- *InfiniWing* replaces the traditional beam in a beam trawl by a hydrofoil that flies above the seabed.
- *InfiniDoor* is a self-adjusting trawl door that can maintain a given distance to the seabed, turning a bottom trawl into a semi-pelagic one.
- *InfiniLog* is a networked datalogger solution for compiling data already generated by fishing vessels or from new sensors like temperature probes, environmental variables of the engine room, fuel consumption, wind, etc.
- *InfiniCatch Jano* is an AI-based DSS for route planning, fishing area selection, and estimation of time-of-arrival, fuel consumption, and fish prices.
- *InfiniCatch Trawl* is a DSS for demersal trawlers which enhances existing logbook software with cloud-based AI for spatial predictions of expected outcomes given current fishing parameters.
- *InfiniCatch NOR* is a DSS aimed at the entire Norwegian fishing fleet, providing spatio-temporal predictions of catch potential based on publicly available data.
- The *Open DSS framework* is a core set of algorithms, models, and interfaces that can be customised and built upon to make operational DSS aimed at specific fisheries, vessel types, or jurisdictions.
- *InfiniSile* is a technology and methodology to implement the on-board collection and silage and viscera for use in aquaculture feed.
- *InfiniSort* is a system for robotic sorting of fish, where fish in a pile or flow are singulated using a robot arm and gripper onto a conveyor, for subsequent scanning and sorting according to species and size.
- *InfiniFood* is a seafood product for human consumption made from non-indigenous species, based on adaptation of current sausage production methods and developing additional value-added products including fish sauce, paste, and kimchi.
- *InfiniGrow* is a plant fertiliser based on silage obtained from fish viscera, remnants, and non-indigenous species that are not suitable for human consumption.

Data will be collected/generated and used in the process of developing, testing, and validating these technologies. With the exception of the Open DSS framework, all the technologies are expected to be commercialised by one or more project partners after the project ends, so much of the data associated with them will be classified as sensitive.

3.2 Classification

Infinifish adheres to the guiding principle: “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”. Accordingly, all shareable data will be made openly available. Such data will be classified as *public* and disseminated in a manner that ensures it is findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable, in line with the FAIR data management principles. We return to this in section 5.

Certain data may not be shared, for one or more of the following reasons:

- to protect the privacy of participants in pilots and social case studies
- to allow for protection of results prior to commercial exploitation
- to protect business sensitive information

Such data will be protected by appropriate security measures and practices, which will be described in section 4.

In particular, data that contain personal information will always be classified as *restricted*. See section 6 for more on this and other ethics issues.

3.3 Data generated in the project

The data sets that will be generated in the project mostly fall into the following categories:

- *Data for technology development.* Data will be collected under laboratory conditions and in early-stage sea trials and used to improve hardware designs, train AI models, adjust process parameters, and more, depending on the technology. These data are mostly sensitive.
- *Data for technology verification and validation.* All technologies will be tested under real or realistic operating conditions, at sea or in on-shore processing plants. Data will be collected and used to assess the efficacy and usability of each technology, and the potential future impact of wide uptake in the industry. These data are mostly sensitive.
- *Output data from ecosystem simulations.* Ecopath with Ecosim will be used to assess the impact of climate change on ecosystems and fisheries. The output of this includes fish stock distribution, abundance, and density, stock productivity, and ecosystem potential production, under different scenarios. Such data will mostly be public.
- *Open software.* Parts of the source code developed for the *InfiniCatch* decision support systems will be released under open source licences. Most of this will be gathered under the *Open DSS framework*.

- *Proprietary software.* Parts of the source code developed for the *InfiniCatch* systems, all of the source code developed for *InfiniSort*, and trained AI models used in these technologies, will be classified as sensitive due to their commercial value for the industry partners.

3.4 Data reused in the project

Some of the project activities involve the reuse of data that have been generated outside the project. Such data sets generally fall under the following categories:

- *Public data.* The *InfiniCatch Jano* and *InfiniCatch NOR* systems will make use of data sets that are published openly by scientific and public institutions. Examples include oceanographic data from the Copernicus Marine Service and fisheries data from the Norwegian Directorate of Fisheries.
- *Data from earlier development.* None of the technologies are developed from scratch, and in some cases data from earlier development stages may be used to further enhance the systems within Infinifish.
- *Ecosystem model inputs.* The ecosystem simulations will be based on existing, area-specific ecosystem models.

4 Storage, sharing, and security

This section describes the plan for storage and sharing of data during the project period, and for long-term archiving of data in private repositories. The plan for open dissemination and archiving of data via *public* repositories is discussed in section 5.

4.1 Platforms

The project will make use of different platforms to store and share data, depending on classification and size. By “platform”, we here mean a hardware and software infrastructure for data handling. Table 4.1 presents an overview, and the individual platforms are described further in the subsections that follow.

All platforms offer similar ways to organise and group information associated with the project and its individual data sets, though they use different terminology. Table 4.2 provides a “translation table” with the various terms.

Table 4.1. Overview of data platforms that the project will use and the kinds of data that may be stored in each. Note that “any” in the *Classification* column includes *restricted* only insofar as the data in question can be shared with SINTEF.

Platform	Classification	Type	Size category
Zenodo	public	any	any
data.sintef.no	any	any	any
SINTEF GitLab	any	software	any
SINTEF SharePoint	internal	any	small, medium

Table 4.2. Platform-specific terms used for the organisational units corresponding to the project and its data sets.

Platform	Project	Data set
Zenodo	community	record
data.sintef.no	data hub	data product
SINTEF GitLab	group	project
SINTEF SharePoint	site/workspace	folder

4.1.1 Zenodo

[Zenodo](#) is a freely usable repository for open publication of research data, hosted by CERN. It will be used as the primary channel for public dissemination of Infinifish research data. We describe the platform and our use of it in section 5.

4.1.2 data.sintef.no

[data.sintef.no](#) is a data repository and cataloguing service developed and hosted by SINTEF for use by the institute's researchers and collaborators. It enables long-term storage and secure sharing of virtually any kind of data. Data can be shared publicly and associated with a DOI, or access can be restricted to specific users and groups.

Infinifish partners can use [data.sintef.no](#) as a data storage and sharing platform for public, internal, and restricted data after agreement with the Data Manager. A data hub has been created for the Infinifish project, and can be found at <https://data.sintef.no/datahub/infinifish> after login.

[data.sintef.no](#) provides research-oriented metadata facilities, though the metadata are not easily exported to any standardised format. Public data products that are assigned a DOI get indexed by DataCite.

Note: Zenodo should be preferred over [data.sintef.no](#) for dissemination of *public* data sets in most cases. This is because Zenodo is much better known and offers richer and more standardised metadata facilities, all of which contribute to greater findability and likelihood of reuse. See section 5.

4.1.3 SINTEF GitLab

[SINTEF GitLab](#) is a platform for building and collaborating on software source code, hosted by SINTEF. It includes planning tools (milestones, issues, tasks, and boards), collaboration tools (repositories and merge requests), continuous integration and deployment tools (pipelines, artifacts), and much more.

Infinifish partners can use [SINTEF GitLab](#) as a software development and collaboration platform for public, internal, and restricted data after agreement with the Data Manager. A group has been created for the Infinifish project, and can be found at <https://gitlab.sintef.no/infinifish>.

Note: While [SINTEF GitLab](#) does allow public access to projects, a user account is always required to engage with the project in the sense of creating or commenting on issues, contributing or reviewing code, and so on. For open source software where direct stakeholder engagement is desired, it is recommended to choose a more widely-used alternative. See section 5.6.3.

4.1.4 SINTEF SharePoint

SINTEF uses Microsoft SharePoint as its intranet platform and document management system. A dedicated SharePoint workspace has been set up for Infinifish, and can be found at <https://sintef.sharepoint.com/teams/work-31171> by users who have been granted access by the coordinator.

This workspace will be the central repository for official documents like contracts, plans, templates, and so on. The partners will primarily use it for sharing and collaborating on documents, spreadsheets, presentations, and similar kinds of files.

It is also possible to use it to share research data internally in the consortium. However, such use should be limited to small, and in special cases medium sized, data sets. This is both because SharePoint imposes a hard limit on individual file sizes, and because large data sets will be an annoyance to users who have enabled automatic synchronisation of workspace contents to their local machine.

Note: SharePoint is not a good platform for public data sharing. It is not searchable by people who don't have an account, its metadata facilities are proprietary and poorly suited for scientific data, and it does not support DOI assignment.

4.1.5 Partners' own platforms

Most project partners have their own systems for storing and managing data. These will usually be the first point of storage for the data that are generated by each partner, and the *only* storage location for some data – especially restricted data.

It is not useful to list all these platforms and their features here. We will only say that it is every partner's responsibility to manage their own data in accordance with their own procedures and requirements, the Grant Agreement, and best data security practices.

4.2 Security aspects

The platforms hosted by the coordinator – data.sintef.no, SINTEF GitLab, and SINTEF SharePoint – are all sufficiently secure for storing *internal* data. Each one requires two-factor authentication (2FA) of users via the *Microsoft Entra ID* identity management service. All communication with the services is protected using the *Transport Layer Security* (TLS) or *Secure Shell* (SSH) cryptographic

protocols. Data is only stored on servers within the European Economic Area and is therefore covered by EU regulations concerning data protection and privacy.

Furthermore, data.sintef.no and SINTEF GitLab (but *not* SINTEF SharePoint) provide sufficiently fine-grained access control that they can also be used to store restricted data, *provided the data can be shared with SINTEF*.

All three platforms are subject to regular off-site back-ups, so storing data there helps to safeguard against data loss.

The responsibilities of the Infinifish partners are:

- For any given data set, make a conscious choice of classification level – public, internal, or restricted – and deposit the data in a platform that provides sufficient security for that level.
- Deposit the data as soon as possible, and no later than 30 days, after it has been generated or collected to minimise the risk of data loss.
- For *internal* data, prefer one of the three aforementioned SINTEF-hosted services – data.sintef.no, SINTEF GitLab, or SINTEF SharePoint – so the data becomes more easily available to the other partners.
- For *internal* or *restricted* data, set access permissions such that only authorised users are able to access the data. In particular, access via so-called “sharing links” should also require authentication.
- For any given data set, report any loss, breach, or corruption immediately to the data’s owner and the Data Manager.

4.3 Data longevity

Data that contains personal information will be irreversibly anonymised or deleted as soon as possible after it has been used for the purpose for which it was collected, and no later than by the end of the project period.

Data stored on SINTEF-hosted services will remain available (though not necessarily *easily* so) for at least 10 years after the end of the project period. Contact the Coordinator or the Data Manager if access is required after the project has ended.

Regarding the longevity of publicly disseminated data, see Section 5.3.

The responsibilities of the Infinifish partners are:

- Deposit data in platforms that provide sufficient longevity guarantees.

- Anonymise or delete personal data as soon as it is no longer needed, at the latest by the end of the project period. (See also section 6 for more information on how to handle personal data.)

5 Open science

Infinifish will manage public data in accordance with the FAIR principles. The aim is to maximise access to, and reuse of, research data generated by the project. The project will use Zenodo as its main tool to achieve this.

Data sets on Zenodo are called *records*, and they are grouped under *communities*. A dedicated community for Infinifish has been created at <https://zenodo.org/communities/infinifish>. The Infinifish community is a special type of community called an *EU project community*, which comes with some added benefits:

- Records published there are indexed in, and available through, the [EU Open Research Repository](#).
- Automated curation checks are performed to ensure compliance with the Horizon Europe open science requirements.
- The community has a “verification checkmark” that signifies to other users that it is officially associated with the project and the EU.

The responsibilities of the Infinifish partners are:

- Classify data generated or collected in the project as *public* unless there exist good reasons not to do so.
- Disseminate public data in accordance with the principles, criteria, and responsibilities described in sections 5.1–5.5.
- Use Zenodo as the dissemination platform unless there exist good reasons to use other repositories. (One such reason would be if using a domain-specific repository increases the probability that the data gets reused. See section 5.5 for more information.)
- Even for data that cannot (yet or ever) be classified as public, consider the principles and responsibilities described in this section as “best practices”, and apply them to the extent possible when handling data as described in section 4.

5.1 The FAIR principles

Below, we quote the FAIR principles in full as they are formulated by GO FAIR, including the specific criteria (in *italic*) that must be fulfilled for a given data set to be considered FAIR.³ In the subsequent sections, we will describe the concrete

³ GO FAIR: *FAIR Principles*. Web site (visited 2025-08-06): <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/> CC BY 4.0.

steps that will be taken to ensure that Infinifish adheres to these principles, how the Zenodo platform aids us in doing so, and the specific responsibilities of the Infinifish partners.

Findable

The first step in (re)using data is to find them. Metadata and data should be easy to find for both humans and computers. Machine-readable metadata are essential for automatic discovery of datasets and services, so this is an essential component of the FAIRification process.

F1. (Meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier.

F2. Data are described with rich metadata (defined by R1 below).

F3. Metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data they describe.

F4. (Meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource.

Accessible

Once the user finds the required data, she/he/they need to know how they can be accessed, possibly including authentication and authorisation.

A1. (Meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardised communications protocol

A1.1 The protocol is open, free, and universally implementable

A1.2 The protocol allows for an authentication and authorisation procedure, where necessary

A2. Metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available

Interoperable

The data usually need to be integrated with other data. In addition, the data need to interoperate with applications or workflows for analysis, storage, and processing.

I1. (Meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.

I2. (Meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles

I3. (Meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data

Reusable

The ultimate goal of FAIR is to optimise the reuse of data. To achieve this, metadata and data should be well-described so that they can be replicated and/or combined in different settings.

R1. (Meta)data are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes

R1.1. (Meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license

R1.2. (Meta)data are associated with detailed provenance

R1.3. (Meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards

5.2 Making data findable

Zenodo supports the creation and assignment of a *Digital Object Identifier* DOI, which is a unique and persistent identifier,⁴ to each published record. The platform also offers a rich set of metadata that can be attached to records:

- resource type (e.g. “data set”, “image”, “publication”, etc.)
- digital object identifier (DOI)
- title
- publication date
- creators (name, affiliations, ORCID)
- description
- licence
- keywords and subjects (using standardised vocabularies)
- contributors (name, affiliations, ORCID)
- publisher (by default Zenodo)
- project name
- funding source and Grant Agreement number

The metadata is indexed and searchable on Zenodo and DataCite. Thus, the use of Zenodo *enables* us to fulfil criteria F1–F3, and *guarantees* that we fulfil F4.

The responsibilities of the Infinifish partners are:

- Assign a DOI to every record when it is created (F1 and F3).

⁴ DOI Foundation: *What is a DOI?* Web site (visited 2025-08-07): <https://www.doi.org/the-identifier/what-is-a-doi/>

- Fill in all the metadata fields of every record (F2).

5.3 Making data accessible

Metadata for records on Zenodo is publicly accessible and licenced under public domain. It is harvestable using the open, free, and universally implementable *Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting* (OAI-PMH). Metadata can also be retrieved using a public REST API.⁵ No authentication or authorisation is ever needed. Zenodo states that metadata *and* data will be available for the lifetime of the repository. This is currently the lifetime of the host institution, CERN, projected to be for at least the next 20 years. Thus, criteria A1 and A2 are automatically fulfilled.

5.4 Making data interoperable

Zenodo uses JSON Schema for its internal representation of metadata. It offers export to several other standard formats, including Dublin Core and MARCXML.

The metadata fields use open vocabularies where relevant, such as Open Definition for licences, OpenAIRE for grants, European Science Vocabulary for keywords/subjects, and so on.

Thus, criteria I1 and I2 are automatically fulfilled for *metadata*. When it comes to the *data*, i.e., the content of records, Zenodo places no restrictions on the format. It is therefore up to the uploader to ensure that the data are interoperable.

The responsibilities of the Infinifish partners are:

- Use open, standard formats whenever feasible (I1). If a particular data set requires the use of a proprietary or unusual file format, attach clear instructions on how the data can be parsed, with links to any required software.
- Represent data using open, well-defined vocabularies when relevant and possible (I2).
- Describe the relationships with other data sets as concretely as possible, preferably in a machine-readable way (I3). For example, specify if a data set builds on, is complemented by, or is completed by another data set, and link to those data sets using their unique identifiers (e.g. DOIs).

⁵ REST stands for “representational state transfer” and API for “application programming interface”. A REST API is way to enable software applications to query web servers for information.

5.5 Making data reusable

Most of the metadata fields on Zenodo records are mandatory, and those are a superset of DataCite's mandatory terms. Others (project name and funding information) are filled out automatically due to the Infinifish community's special status as an EU project community. Metadata on Zenodo is always published under the CC0 public domain waiver, ensuring that anyone can use it, at any time, for any purpose, with no restrictions.

Thus, criterion R1 is fulfilled by default for *metadata*. It is the uploader's responsibility to ensure that the *data* are reusable.

The responsibilities of the Infinifish partners are:

- Document the data to the extent necessary to facilitate its reuse (R1). In particular, provide information about how to interpret the data and how to process it (e.g. variable definitions, units of measurement, required software, example code, and so on). The documentation may be provided in one or more of the following forms, in order of preference:
 - as part of the record metadata on Zenodo
 - as metadata embedded in the data files (when the file format supports it)
 - as separate documents (e.g. a *Readme* file) within the record
 - with a reference to an openly published paper or report
- Publish the data under the [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International](#) (CC-BY) licence or a similarly permissive licence⁶ (R1.1). This enables anyone to copy, redistribute, remix, transform, and build upon the material for any purpose, even commercially, provided they give appropriate credit and indicate if changes were made.
- Provide detailed information about the provenance of the data (R1.2). Include information about how the data was generated/collected and how it has been processed. If the data or the workflow by which it was generated/collected/used is described in a published article or report, include its unique identifier (DOI or similar) in the description.

⁶ More permissive licences such as CC0 may be used, or, if deemed necessary, more restrictive ones such as [Creative Commons Attribution-NoDerivatives 4.0 International](#) (CC BY-ND). Such decisions will be made on a case-by-case basis in deliberation with the Coordinator, the Innovation and Exploitation Manager, and the involved partners.

- Adhere to relevant domain-specific standards or best practices if such exist (R1.3). This could entail choosing the most commonly used file formats or templates, including additional metadata, and so on. *It could also mean using a different repository than Zenodo*, as long as the repository in question supports adherence to FAIR principles in the manner described here.

5.6 Special cases

Some types of data benefit greatly from being disseminated through channels or services that are more specialised or enable a greater degree of stakeholder engagement than a plain data repository.

5.6.1 Scientific publications

Academic papers that are generated as a result of the project will be published in peer-reviewed journals under open access conditions as required by the Grant Agreement, Annex 5. There are two main routes to this:

- “Gold” open access: The paper is made openly available via the journal itself.
- “Green” open access: A copy of the published paper or final peer-reviewed manuscript (postprint) is deposited in a public repository.

As always, Zenodo is a good default choice in the latter case. However, there exist dedicated archives for this purpose⁷ that are widely used in some disciplines, which may therefore be a better choice.

The responsibilities of the Infinifish partners are:

- Prefer journals that provide open access to published articles under CC BY or a licence with equivalent rights.
- When publishing in journals with stricter access conditions, and no later than the time of publication, deposit a copy of the published version or a postprint in a public repository in accordance with the principles and responsibilities described in sections 5.1–5.5.
- Do not publish in journals that allow none of these alternatives.

⁷ sometimes called “preprint servers”

- Consider publishing *preprints* of papers too, i.e., manuscripts that have not yet been peer reviewed. This speeds up the dissemination of research results and can help to engage with the scientific community.

5.6.2 Public deliverables

Deliverables that are classified as *public* are automatically published on the [CORDIS platform](#) as soon as they have been approved by the granting authority. They will also be uploaded by the coordinator to the Infinifish community on Zenodo.

The responsibilities of the Infinifish partners are:

- Consider whether deliverables classified as *sensitive* in the Grant Agreement can be reclassified as *public* and published openly.
- Consider publishing preprints of public deliverables, i.e., versions that have not yet been approved by the granting authority. This speeds up the dissemination of research results and can help to engage with the scientific community.

5.6.3 Software

There exists a whole ecosystem surrounding what is called *free and open source software* (FOSS), with specialised licences, open collaboration platforms, and a rich selection of available tools. Making use of these can significantly increase the engagement of stakeholders in the scientific community, in industry, and in the open source community at large.

The responsibilities of the Infinifish partners are:

- Consider publishing the source code openly using a code collaboration platform like [GitHub](#), [Codeberg.org](#), [Sourcehut](#), or similar.
- Release the software under [a licence approved by the Open Source Initiative](#) (OSI). These are licences that comply with the *Open Source Definition*, allowing the software to be freely used, modified, and shared.
- Consider publishing the software at an early stage and doing the development in the open, perhaps even to the extent of accepting bug reports and contributions from stakeholders outside the project.
- Whenever open source software created in Infinifish is used within the project to
 - generate open data

- perform analyses, simulations, or similar as part of a published paper or report

then a copy of the source code for the specific version of the software that was used must be uploaded to a repository where it can be assigned a DOI and thus linked to the data/publications in question. By default, this will be Zenodo.⁸ The responsibilities listed in sections 5.2–5.5 also apply here.

- If no version has been archived as described in the previous point by the end of the project, do so then.

⁸ Note that GitHub and Zenodo have a [special integration](#) that automates some of this.

6 Ethics

The work in Infinifish is carried out in full compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation⁹ (GDPR). In addition, Infinifish complies with the principles of the European Charter for Researchers¹⁰ and the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity,¹¹ including ethical standards and guidelines, regardless of the country in which research is carried out.

Nothing in this project shall be deemed to require a party to breach any mandatory statutory law under which the party is operating. This includes any national or European regulations, rules, and norms regarding ethics in conducting research.

6.1 Ethics advisory services

In matters of data protection and privacy, the project has access to the advisory services of Sikt, the *Norwegian Agency for Shared Services in Education and Research*.¹² The coordinator, SINTEF, has an agreement with Sikt for data protection services.

In matters of research ethics more generally, including for example the use of animals and the development of AI systems, the project has access to the advisory services of NENT, the *Norwegian National Committee for Research Ethics in Science and Technology*.¹³ They provide advice and guidance on research in science and technology, as well as industrial, agricultural, and fisheries research.

An Ethics Mentor is appointed by the coordinator to advise the participants on the ethics issues raised by the research activities, in particular the collection of personal data on human participants in pilots and social case studies, the involvement of animals in fishing trials, the environmental impact assessment of new technologies to be deployed, and health and safety measures for individuals

⁹ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation). <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679>.

¹⁰ Commission Recommendation of 11 March 2005 on the European Charter for Researchers and on a Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reco/2005/251>.

¹¹ ALLEA (2023): *The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity – Revised Edition 2023*. [doi:10.26356/ECOC](https://doi.org/10.26356/ECOC).

¹² Sikt: *Data protection services*. Web site. <https://sikt.no/en/omrade/Data-Protection>.

¹³ National Research Ethics Committees: *About NENT*. Web site. <https://www.forskningsetikk.no/en/about-us/our-committees-and-commission/nent/about-nent>.

involved in technology testing. The Ethics Mentor will keep records of these advisory activities on file. Currently, this role is held by [Ingunn Marie Holmen](#), SINTEF Ocean.

Partners who wish to consult any of the above should do so via the coordinator.

6.2 Data that contain personal information

Some of the data sets generated in Infinifish contain personal information. Such data will always be classified as restricted and will only be shared with project participants that have a legitimate need for it in order to implement the project in accordance with the Grant Agreement.

Data containing personal information may only be reclassified as public or internal after it has been irreversibly anonymised.

Non-anonymous data, although not shared openly within the project or beyond, can still provide input to deliverables and publications, as long as these only present anonymised excerpts or analyses of the aggregated data, and no details that can be linked to individuals.

The responsibilities of the Infinifish partners are:

- Obtain approval from an ethics committee, data protection officer, or similar body before starting any task that involves the collection and/or processing of personal information.¹⁴
- Keep records of both the request and the approval. Send these documents to the coordinator, along with a summary in English if the documents are in another language.
- Irreversibly anonymise or delete data containing personal information as soon as they are no longer needed for the implementation of the project, and no later than by the end of the project.

6.3 Pictures and video for communication purposes

Infinifish will collect pictures and videos for use in communication activities, including the project web site, social media, and more. Such data will only be collected with prior consent from the people involved and only used for as long

¹⁴ Note that the Grant Agreement wrongly states that Sikt can do such evaluation for any partner. This is an error; they can only evaluate activities where SINTEF is responsible for the data collection. Each partner should use a national, local, or institutional ethics body for this. The Grant Agreement will be amended to correct this error.

as consent is given. Pictures and video can contain personal data if an individual is the focus of the image or video. Examples include:

1. pictures/video of individuals stored together with personal details (e.g. identity cards)
2. pictures/video of individuals posted on the project website along with biographical details
3. individual images published in a newsletter

Examples of pictures and video that are *unlikely* to contain personal data are:

1. pictures/video where people are incidentally included in an image or are not the focus (e.g. at a big conference/workshop)
2. images of people who are no longer alive¹⁵

When collecting pictures and video, Infinifish will follow established guidance and best practice on collecting and processing such data to ensure that we adhere to the legal requirements. Under no circumstances will pictures containing personal information be shared publicly without the subject's explicit consent.

¹⁵ The GDPR only applies to living people.

7 Allocation of resources

The three data platforms that are hosted by the coordinator – data.sintef.no, SINTEF GitLab, and SINTEF SharePoint – are financed internally by SINTEF. Their use does not incur direct costs to the project or the project partners.

Zenodo is free to use, as are most of the alternative public repositories.

The personnel costs associated with data management are subsumed under Work Package 1, *Project management and coordination*, in the Infinifish budget.

Additional, unforeseen costs associated with data management will be handled on a case-by-case basis.